

4th Workshop HPC-TRES

OGS Report: 2022/67 Sez. OCE 48

Book of abstracts

December 2nd, 2021 - Virtual Meeting

High
Performance
Computing

Training and
Research for
Earth
Sciences

HPC-TRES website: <http://www.ogs.trieste.it/en/content/hpc-training-and-research-earth-sciences-hpc-tres>

www.ogs.it

OGS

National Institute
of Oceanography
and Applied
Geophysics

www.cineca.it

**Edited by: M. Zanenghi, V. Mosetti, S. Salon
Trieste, April 2022**

HPC-TRES program, web page:

<http://www.ogs.trieste.it/en/content/hpc-training-and-research-earth-sciences-hpc-tres>

4th Workshop HPC-TRES

High Performance Computing – Training and Research for Earth Sciences
December 2nd 2021, Virtual Meeting

The HPC-TRES program

HPC-TRES is a national initiative promoted by OGS and CINECA aimed to implement a training program focused on High Performance Computing (HPC) applications for Earth Sciences. HPC-TRES is co-sponsored by the Minister of University and Research (MUR) under the Italian Research Infrastructure **PRACE-Italy**, the MUR contribute for the Italian participation to activities related to the European infrastructure PRACE – The Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe.

The major objectives of the program are capacity building, enhancement of human resources, and advanced training in the fields of Earth System modelling (atmosphere, hydrosphere, lithosphere and biosphere) and numerical models, the latter considered as a strategic cross-cutting element for modelling activities. These objectives are pursued by exploiting the national and European HPC infrastructures and services in the framework of PRACE and PRACE-Italy, the optimization of algorithms and numerical codes, the optimal management of “Earth Sciences Big Data”, and the graphical visualization techniques for multidisciplinary applications in the Earth Sciences, also in the frame of the “Blue Growth” strategy.

Therefore, the HPC-TRES program establishes, sponsors and oversees training and research awards (in the form of scholarships grants) that support the research lines described in the scientific plan of the HPC-TRES program¹. Many Italian research groups and institutions involved in HPC applications for Earth Sciences (INGV-Pisa, CNR/ISAC, CNR/IGG, CMCC, ICTP-ESP, MOX-Politecnico di Milano, ENEA-SSPT, INGV-SST, INGV-CNT, Univ. Bicocca, CRS4, EURAC, ARPA-FVG, Fondazione CIMA, Univ. Genova, Univ. Trieste, Consorzio LAMMA, INAF-OATs) have already endorsed the HPC-TRES initiative, contributing to the HPC-TRES scientific plan.

The 4th HPC-TRES workshop

The 4th workshop of HPC-TRES was organized by OGS as a virtual meeting, due to the restrictions imposed by the COVID-19 emergency. The main objectives were: to share a common discussion with all the research groups that contribute to the HPC-TRES scientific plan, to present the status and the current outcomes of the research activities, to highlight the future perspectives of the national HPC infrastructure and to offer an opportunity of cross-discipline contamination, supported by the common HPC background which characterizes the different scientific approaches adopted by the research groups involved in the program.

A total of 31 attendees participated to the workshop, with 20 past and present HPC-TRES grantees (40% of the total grants acknowledged by the program in the period 2014-2021). Among them, 18 presented the main results of their research work, highlighting the scientific and technological challenges they have coped with. Modelling studies at different spatial and temporal scales, implementation of innovative algorithms, model optimization, HPC model data management, covered different Earth Sciences topics: from global to regional climate, atmosphere, ocean, hydrology, volcanic and earthquakes studies.

Tab. 1 shows the list of participants, some information related to the reference HPC-TRES research

¹ Available at https://www.ogs.it/sites/default/files/hpc-tres-scientificplan-topicslines_3_0.pdf

line where they are involved, and the title of the presentations. The abstracts of the presentations are included in the present report.

The three previous workshop editions are available on Zenodo (indexed in OpenAIRE), respectively at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5993708> (2018), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5993775> (2019) and <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5993814> (2020).

Tab. 1 – List of participants (with affiliations), and notes including role, HPC-TRES research lines (if present), and title of presentation.

	Name, institution	Notes (role, research line, title of presentation)
1	Julie Baron, Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS	Numerical simulation of earthquake ground motion in Arquata del Tronto (B1)
2	Stefano Campanella, Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS	Massive earthquake template matching on GPUs using modern Python (B8)
3	Mattia Carello, Università di Bologna - UNIBO	A 2D ERTM framework * (B10)
4	Alessandro D'Anca, Centro euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC)	(E1)
5	Alessandro Damiani, Università di Pavia - IUSS Pavia	The role of HPC in scenario-based risk assessment: the case study of Isfahan, Iran (B12)
6	Eleonora Denich, Università di Trieste e Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS	Numerical methods for electromagnetic inversion (B3)
7	Fabien Desbiolles, Università di Milano Bicocca	Atmospheric response to Ocean mesoscales (D5)
8	Fabio Di Sante, Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS	Future projections of river floods (C6)
9	Donatello Elia, Centro euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC)	(E1)

10	Tomaso Esposti Ongaro, Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia - INGV	Steering Committee (B5, B6, B7, C4)
11	Matilde García-Valdecasas Ojeda, International Centre for Theoretical Physics - ICTP	The Effect of Correcting Sub-daily Climate Model Outputs: Implications for Hydrological Studies of Extreme Values * (C6)
12	Endalkachew Gelaw, University of Genoa	Coupling Atmospheric and Hydrological Modelling in the Context of Parallel Computing (D7)
13	Andrea Giannotta, Centro euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC)	HPCaaS for climate data analytics at scale (E1)
14	Francesco Immorlano, Università del Salento e Centro euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC)	Machine Learning for Extreme Weather Events (E1)
15	Peter Klin, Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS	(B1, B2)
16	Celia Laurent, Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS	(A3, A4)
17	Andrea Magrin, Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS	(B15)
18	Chiara Montagna, Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia - INGV	(B6)
19	Manuel Musio, Centro euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici (CMCC)	A HPC-enabled solution for the management of large climate analytics workflows (E1)
20	Rita Nogherotto, Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS	Projections of the Fire Weather Index (FWI) using CORDEX-CORE simulations (C6)

21	Michele Petrini, Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale (C5) - OGS	
22	Giovanni Petris, Università degli Studi di Trieste	Marine Propeller Noise Propagation within a Shallow Water Environment (A7)
23	Gloria Pietropoli, Università degli Studi di Trieste	Inpainting method for modelling the Mediterranean Sea (A1)
24	Marco Reale, Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale (D3) - OGS	
25	Chiara Scaini, Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS	The role of HPC in scenario-based risk assessment: the case study of Isfahan, Iran (B12)
26	Umberta Tinivella, Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS	(B16, E6)
27	Lavinia Tunini, Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS	GPS coordinate time series in NE-Italy (B15)
28	Aldo Vesnaver, Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale (B3) - OGS	
29	Jost von Hardenberg, Politecnico di Torino e Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate (CNR-ISAC)	Steering Committee (D2)
30	Luigi Sante Zampa, Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS	Restoration of vintage gravity data and comparison with new satellite-derived models: Two case studies (B11)
31	Maria Zanenghi, OGS	Logistic Support

Acknowledgements

The 4th HPC-TRES workshop was supported by OGS thanks to the MUR grant “PRACE-Italy”, under the extraordinary contribute for the Italian participation to activities related to the international infrastructure PRACE – The Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe.

We acknowledge Maria Zanenghi and William Toson (OGS) for the logistic support in the organization of the virtual meeting.

The HPC-TRES Steering Committee:

Cosimo Solidoro (OGS, Trieste)

Filippo Giorgi (ICTP, Trieste)

Tomaso Esposti Ongaro (INGV, Pisa)

Antonello Provenzale (CNR-IGG, Pisa)

Giovanni Aloisio (Univ. Salento e CMCC, Lecce)

Jost von Hardenberg (Politecnico di Torino – DIATI, Torino)

Eric Pascolo (CINECA, Bologna)

Stefano Salon (OGS, Trieste)

Index

page	Name, institution	Title of presentation
9	Baron, J., OGS	Numerical simulation of earthquake ground motion in Arquata del Tronto (Italy)
11	Campanella, S., OGS	Earthquake template-matching at scale using GPUs and modern Python
13	Carello, M., Università di Bologna	2D Elastic Reverse Time Migration framework
15	Denich, E., Università di Trieste	Numerical methods for electromagnetic inversion
17	Desbiolles F., Università di Milano - OGS	Influence of the aerosol concentration and ocean properties on the atmospheric boundary layer and the associated rainfall
19	Di Sante, F., OGS - ICTP	Future projections of river floods
21	García-Valdecasas Ojeda, M., OGS - ICTP	The effect of correcting sub-daily climate outputs: implications for hydrological studies of extreme values
23	Gelaw, E. B., (DIBRIS) Università di Genova - CIMA	Coupling atmospheric and hydrological modelling in the context of parallel computing
25	Giannotta, A., CMCC	HPCaaS for climate data analytics at scale
27	Immorlano, F., Università del Salento - CMCC	Machine Learning for Extreme Weather Events
29	Musio, M., CMCC	An HPC-enabled solution for the management of large climate analytics workflows
31	Nogherotto, R., OGS - ICTP	Projections of the Fire Weather Index (FWI) using CORDEX-CORE simulations
33	Petris, G., Università di Trieste	Marine Propeller Noise Propagation within a Shallow Water Environment
35	Pietropolli, G., Università di Trieste - OGS	Multivariate relationship in big data collection of Ocean Observing System
37	Scaini, C., OGS	The role of HPC in scenario-based risk assessment: the case study of Isfahan, Iran
39	Tunini, L., OGS	GPS coordinate time series in NE-Italy
41	Zampa L. S, OGS - Università di Trieste	Gravity data restoration and modeling for the identification of buried geological structures

Numerical simulation of earthquake ground motion in Arquata del Tronto (Italy)

Baron, J. and Klin, P.

Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS, Borgo Grotta, Italy

Keywords: numerical simulation, topographic site effect, Arquata del Tronto

The combined effect of topography and near-surface heterogeneities on the seismic response is hardly predictable and may lead to an aggravation of the ground motion. We apply physics-based numerical simulations of 3D seismic wave propagation to highlight these effects in the case study of Arquata del Tronto, a hamlet in the Central Appenines, Italy, that suffered irregularly distributed damage during the 2016 Amatrice seismic sequence. Located on an elongated WNW-ESE ridge at an elevation of about 100 meters above the underlying valley, Arquata del Tronto hamlet suffered extensive damage and collapses (MCS VIII-IX), while the Borgo fraction located only 200 meters north, in the valley, reported lighter damages (MCS VII), suggesting that topography related modifications of earthquake ground motion took place in the area.

The present work is a continuation of a previous analysis, where we set up a 3D digital model of the area and evaluated the resulting ground motion by means of 3D numerical simulations of seismic wave propagation (Primofiore et al., 2020). In order to provide easily generalizable results and some new insights in respect to the topography-related site effects, we iterate the numerical evaluation of ground motion for three different versions of the Arquata del Tronto structural model, with growing complexity. The first version is characterized by a homogeneous structure, the second one presents near surface alterations (weathering layer and a restricted soil basin over a flat area), and the third one exhibits a complex three dimensional structure and corresponds to the one used in our previous study. We analyze the separated and combined effects of irregular topography and subsurface heterogeneity on the seismic ground motion in terms of horizontal component spectral amplification and polarization and investigate the possible correlation between ground motion parameters and topographic parameters.

In our approach, we employ 3D impulse response functions evaluated from 3D physics-based numerical simulations of seismic wave propagation (Paolucci, 1999) and we evaluate the numerical solutions for vertically incident polarized plane waves in a reference spatial domain, characterized by a homogeneous medium and flat topographic surface. In order to estimate the site average amplification and its multiplicative standard deviation, our seismic inputs are a set of 200 three component seismic signals, collected in a station on seismic bedrock in the same geographical area and recorded during the 2016 Amatrice seismic sequence.

We perform numerical simulation of the seismic ground motion using the Spectral Element Method and the SPECFEM3D software. The 3D domain of Arquata del Tronto is embeded in a 3 km long side square volume aligned with the cardinal directions, extending from a depth of 500 m b.s.l. to the top surface which honors a 10 m resolution digital elevation map. We discretized the spatial domain with an unstructured mesh, made of 518.400 hexahedral elements. Spectral elements are approximately 25 m size near the top of the volume, where the low seismic velocities that characterize the alteration layer and alluvial deposits imply shorter wavelengths. On the other hand, we set an element size of 50 m in the lower part of the volume, where seismic velocities are higher. A 75 meters thick Perfectly Matched Layer was applied on the lateral and bottom boundaries of the volume in order to exclude artefact reflections from the numerical solution. The obtained results highlight the frequency dependence of topography-related amplification, which is controlled by topographic features with characteristic sizes comparable with the associated wavelength.

Following an approach introduced by Maufroy et al. (2015), we find a correlation between

frequency-scaled topographic curvature and amplification. Finally, we analyze the possibility of topography-induced torsional motions in terms of the scaling factor between the induced rotation rate and the seismic input acceleration and find a linear proportionality between the scaling factor and the tangent of the topographic slope. This finding suggests that induced torsional motion could concur in the aggravation of earthquake effects on rocky hills like the one on which Arquata del Tronto rests.

Fig1. Linear correlation between the scaling factor A_{θ} and the topographic slope for seismic ground motion numerical simulation computed in the Arquata del Tronto homogeneous model AdT0.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2017-22. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the ISCRA initiative, for the availability of high performance computing resources and support (IscraC "SERATA", OGS18_PRACE_P).

References

- Maufroy E, Cruz-Atienza VM, Cotton F, Gaffet S (2015) Frequency-scaled curvature as a proxy for topographic site-effect amplification and ground-motion variability. *Bull Seismol Soc Am* 105:354–367. <https://doi.org/10.1785/0120140089>
- Paolucci R (1999) Numerical evaluation of the effect of cross-coupling of different components of ground motion in site response analyses. *Bull Seismol Soc Am* 89:877–887
- Primofiore et al., 2020, 3D numerical modelling for interpreting topographic effects in rocky hills for Seismic Microzonation: The case study of Arquata del Tronto hamlet, *Engineering Geology*, Volume 279

Earthquake template-matching at scale using GPUs and modern Python

Campanella, S., Vuan, A., Sukan, M.

Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS, Trieste, Italy

Keywords: template-matching, GPU

Template-matching is an algorithm to find the part of a signal which match a given template. It's usage in seismology allows to augment existing catalogue and detect events in continuous waveforms that other algorithms are not able to detect. These events are usually small earthquakes with signals close to the noise level. Template-matching has advantages and drawbacks compared to other algorithms, and it's a valuable tool for the study of micro-seismicity. It is a CPU-bounded algorithm, and its time complexity scales linearly with the size of the templates catalogue, the length of the template waveforms and of the continuous data. In practice, large scale analyses require some expedients to be feasible.

In this work we used template-matching to analyse a catalogue of 48,000 events and 8 years of continuous data concerning the pre-sequence of the Amatrice earthquake of 2016, within the context of the Horizon 2020 project RISE. The purpose was, on the one hand, to enhance the statistics of the existing catalogue and, on the other, to illuminate possible seismogenic processes. This analysis required a complete rewrite of an existing code, PyMPA (Vuan et al. 2017), including a porting to GPU. In a first phase, all the core routines of the program were optimized and debugged. These optimizations concerned mainly the IO and error handling. Afterwards, to take full advantage of the potential of Marconi 100, with which the analysis was performed, a new code has been developed, with support for threading, GPUs, and including other algorithmic optimizations.

The improvements with respect to the original version can be summarized as follows.

- Performance: 200% speedup using a single thread, linear scaling with multithreading, GPU support, efficient serialization using Apache AVRO and Parquet.
- Algorithmic: enhanced detection capability, more robust estimation of magnitude and of cross-correlation, better utilization and handling of continuous data.
- Usability and maintainability: less code and dependencies, enhanced readability, easier deployment via a package published on PyPi, reworked command line interface and logging capability

Thanks to the resources granted by the ISCRA C: SPACE - HP10CGW5X9, submitted for the purpose, it was possible to complete the analysis in less than one thousand core-hours (the others being currently used for further analyses).

Fig.1 – Example of detection using template-matching (PyMPA)

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2021-48. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the ISCR initiative, for the availability of high performance computing resources and support (ISCR C “SPACE”).

References

Vuan A., Sukan M., Amati G., Kato A. (2017) Improving the Detection of Low-Magnitude Seismicity Preceding the Mw 6.3 L'Aquila Earthquake: Development of a Scalable Code Based on the Cross-Correlation of Template Earthquakes, BSSA

2D Elastic Reverse Time Migration framework

Carello, M.¹, Theis, D.², Bonomi, E.²

¹Università "Alma Mater Studiorum", Bologna, Italy

²CRS4, Firenze, Pula (CA), Italy

Keywords: RTM, reverse time migration, HPC, Poynting vector, seismic explorations, migration method, exploratory 3D surveys, MPI, parallel computing

Reverse Time Migration (RTM) is not a new imaging technique, it was invented in 1983 by Baisal, Kosloff and Sherwood in order to offer improvements over existing migration methods, especially in cases of steeply dipping structures with strong velocity contrasts. However, it was not until the late 1990s and mainly the 2000s that computational advances allowed the geophysical community to use this technology for exploratory 3D surveys. RTM's propagation engine, a two-way wave equation, makes this imaging method robust and accurate because it honors the kinematics of the wave phenomena by allowing waves to propagate in all direction regardless velocity model or the direction of propagation. Nevertheless, RTM has its limitations. Two major drawbacks are the artifacts produced by backscattering and the amplitudes of the migrated images, which are not proportional to the subsurface reflectivity.

We built an RTM code starting from an acoustic elastic propagation code, the SimSonic software. SimSonic is freely available 3rd party software suite for the simulation of ultrasound propagation, based on finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) computations of the elastodynamics equations. The SimSonic suite consists of several compiled programs and C source codes, free for use. We used this code as reference. But for the purpose, it was necessary to edit the code to build the whole workflow of the RTM. We implemented an MPI parallelization paradigm to lower the disk occupation and save time.

To reduce the artifacts caused by backscattering and crosstalk events we used the Poynting-vector imaging condition. Several attempts to improve the amplitudes are conducted, they are based on the Helmholtz decomposition of the wavefield. In order to obtain an high resolution image of the subsurface reflectivity, we implemented the following changes to forward and backward propagator, which are based on SimSonic software: clean trace from direct arrivals, reverse time, record P- and S-wave signal separately, computation of Poynting vectors and their usage by means of masks in the imaging condition step.

We established two levels of code parallelization, in order to have results in hours, not in days, and a low consumption of memory: single shot level and multiple shots level. For the first case, we can run simultaneously two synchronized processes to compute the contributions of the imaging condition at each snapshot time, in this fashion we save disk space and time. Since is important to carry out many shots, for the second case, a process must be in charge of summing the image contributions coming from a single shot to generate the final image. The main consequence of this choice was to save time.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2019-06. We acknowledge the CRS4 for the availability of high performance computing resources and support.

References

Edip Baysal, Dan D. Kosloff, and John W. C. Sherwood, Reverse time migration, *Geophysics* 48 (1983), no. 11, 1514–1524

B. Biondi, 3-D Seismic Imaging , *Investigations of Geophysics*, vol. 14, Society of Exploration Geophysicists, 2006

S. Chattopadhyay and G. McMechan, Imaging conditions for prestack reverse time migration, *Geophysics* 73 (2008), no. 3, 81–89

M. Cogan, R. Fletcher, R. King, and D. Nichols, Normalization strategies for reverse-time migration, *SEG Annual meeting Society of Exploration Geophysicists* (2011), 3275–3279

J. Costa, F. Silva, R. Alcántara, J. Schleicher, and A. Novais, Obliquity-correction imaging condition for reverse time migration, *Geophysics* 74 (2009), no. 3, S57–S66

K. Yoon and K. Marfurt, Reverse time migration using the Poynting vector, *Exploration Geophysics* 37 (2006), 102–107

Diaz E., Sava P. (2015) Understanding the reverse time migration backscattering: noise or signal? <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2478.12232>

Numerical methods for electromagnetic inversion

Denich, E.¹, Novati, P.¹, and Picotti, S.²

¹Università degli studi di Trieste, Trieste, Italy

²Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS, Trieste, Italy

Keywords: Maxwell equations, Gauss-Kronrod quadrature, EM response, EM inversion

The aim of electromagnetic (EM) soundings methods in geophysics is to obtain information about the conductivity structure of the earth by recorded measurements taken at the surface. One technique consists of placing a magnetic dipole above the surface. In this case, the electromagnetic induction effect, encoded in Maxwell's equations, produce eddy alternating currents in the soil which on their turn, induce response electromagnetic fields, that can be used to determine the conductivity profile of the ground. Among the available instruments, the DUALEM (DUAL-geometry Electro-Magnetic; <http://www.dualem.com>) system is often used. The receiver couples are placed at 2,4,6 and 8 m from the transmitter coil, and typical source-receiver geometries are the horizontal coplanar (HCP configuration) and perpendicular (PRP configuration) coils.

We consider a specific application, related to the internal composition of river levees. They may collapse due to the condition of the soils that form the embankment, since water seepage throughout the embankment could generate internal erosion.

To reconstruct geophysical structures from EM measurements, an inversion procedure is needed. One typically defines a forward model for the EM response and then minimize the mismatch between the measured data and the predicted data. The forward model used in the inversion usually consists of a set of locally horizontal homogeneous layers. Under this assumption, general integral solutions of Maxwell equations for vertical and horizontal magnetic dipoles can be derived and represented as Hankel transforms, that in general are not analytically computable. Therefore, a numerical scheme is needed. Anyway, the slowly decay of the oscillations determined by the presence of the Bessel function inside the integral makes the problem very difficult to handle, because traditional quadrature rules typically fail to converge. To numerically evaluate this kind of integrals, the digital filter algorithm was introduced. This method is essentially a standard quadrature rule, but the main difference is that the weights are computed by solving a linear equation obtained by imposing the rule to be correct on a set of training functions (not polynomials) for which the corresponding integral is known.

We consider a different approach based on the splitting of the integrand function in a first function, for which the corresponding integral is known exactly, and a second oscillating function that decays exponentially and for which the corresponding integral can be accurately computed by a classical quadrature rule on finite intervals.

We also consider the inverse problem of computing the model parameters (i.e. conductivity and thickness of the layers) from a set of measured field values at different offsets. To this purpose, we employ two optimization algorithms based on the BFGS line-search method and on the Simulated Annealing global-search technique. In order to reduce as much as possible the number of integral evaluations, we also derive an analytical approximation of these integrals that can be used in the initial iterations of the inversion procedure to have a first estimate of the solution.

The numerical experiments confirm the reliability of these techniques. Furthermore, while the two methods show very similar performances in terms of solution accuracy, the BFGS is more than 10 times faster than the Simulated Annealing. This asset of the BFGS method enables its application to the inversion of large datasets.

Fig.1 – Comparison between the magnetic fields computed adopting the numerical Gauss-Kronrod quadrature technique (solid lines), the analytical approximation (dashed lines) and the numerical digital filtering algorithm (symbols). The two components of the magnetic field correspond to the HPC and PRP configurations, respectively. Two different layered underground models are considered.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2019-04.

This research has been funded by the DILEMMA project, “Imaging, modelling, monitoring and design of earthen levees”; Ministero dell’Ambiente e della Tutela del Territorio e del Mare (MATTM), under the framework “Progetti di ricerca finalizzati alla previsione e alla prevenzione dei rischi geologici” (D.D. 524 del 29 novembre 2017).

References

- Denich, E., Novati, P. and Picotti, S. (2021), A fast and accurate numerical approach for electromagnetic inversion, preprint.
- Ghosh, D. P., (1971), The application of linear filter theory to the direct interpretation of geoelectrical resistivity sounding measurements, *Geophysical Prospecting* 19 (2), 192-217.
- Singh, N.P. and Mogi, T. (2010), EMDPLER: A F77 program for modelling the EM response of dipolar sources over the non-magnetic layer earth models, *Computer & Geosciences*, 36, 430-440.
- Wait, J.R. (1962), A note on the electromagnetic response of a stratified Earth, *Geophysics*, 27,382-385.
- Ward, S.H. and Hohmann, G.W. (1988) Electromagnetic theory for geophysical applications. In: Nabighian, M.N., (ed.), *Electromagnetic Methods in Applied Geophysics, Theory vol. 1*. Society of Exploration Geophysicists, Tulsa, Oklahoma, pp. 131-311.

Influence of the aerosol concentration and ocean properties on the atmospheric boundary layer and the associated rainfall

Desbiolles F.¹, Meroni A. N.¹, Napoli A.² and Pasquero C.^{1,3}

¹Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences, Università di Milano, Italy

²CIMA Foundation, Savona, Italy

³Istituto di Scienze dell'Atmosfera e del Clima, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Turin, Italy

Keywords: boundary layer, air-sea interactions, aerosols

One of the larger challenges facing the climate modeling community is that climate models appear to poorly represent some of the key regional circulation processes and as a result, struggle to produce reasonable simulations of regional rainfall patterns. The difficulty is partly due to the regional climate dynamics being complex and strongly modulated by processes operating on the global scale down to regional and local scales. Notably, over the ocean, interactions at the interface influence the thermodynamical balance and the exchange of key properties, controlling the dynamics of both fluids over a wide spectrum of variability. The local heat and momentum fluxes are then shaping the vertical structures of the atmosphere and the ocean, basin-scale circulations, climate and therefore water cycle. Moreover, in addition to those air-sea fluxes, aerosol composition of the air-column also alters the thermodynamics through different feedback mechanisms, affecting radiation, clouds and air-column stability. The alteration of Earth's radiative budget through both direct and indirect effects is paramount for climate studies.

Two main mechanisms have been proposed to describe the Marine Atmospheric Boundary Layer (MABL) response to small-scale spatial and temporal variability of Sea Surface Temperature (SST). The so-called Downward Momentum (DM) flux mixing mechanism and the Pressure Adjustment (PA) mechanism. The DM mechanism brings into play the turbulence and large eddies with the MABL stimulated by the turbulent fluctuations of momentum, temperature and moisture; themselves driven by SST gradient. The PA mechanism, initially proposed in a context of tropical dynamics, causes wind divergence in the MABL due to surface atmospheric pressure forced by temperature patterns. It ensues a linear relationship between the anomaly of the across-wind component of the wind divergence and across-wind component of the Laplacian of SST [Meroni et al., in rev.]. The above two mechanisms operate from meso- to submesoscales but it remains unclear the favorable conditions which makes one process prevailing on the other-one.

Over the Mediterranean, we first show that the DM mechanism is prevailing at daily time scale notably due to the stable nature of the air-column over the Mediterranean. Autumn season is the period during which the DM mechanism is more determining for the surface wind speed. We then show the corresponding vertical structure of the MABL over SST patterns, with a significant imprint until 925 hPa. Finally we show that the downwind SST gradient modifies significantly cloud cover, reducing when the flows corresponds to warm-to-cold SST patterns, increasing for a cold-to-warm scenario. Rainfall events are significantly more (less) frequent over extreme negative (positive) Downwind SST gradients [Desbiolles et al., 2021]. More specifically, the 25% strongest warm-to-cold fronts are associated with a mean increase of cloud cover of $10 \pm 5\%$ ($25 \pm 12\%$) and a mean increase in the probability of a rain event of $15 \pm 6\%$ ($22 \pm 10\%$), with respect to the average values for the entire period (Fall only). The 25% strongest cold-to-warm fronts are associated with a mean decrease of cloud cover of $4 \pm 2\%$ ($14 \pm 8\%$) and a mean decrease in the probability of a rain event of $10 \pm 4\%$ ($18 \pm 8\%$) for the entire period (Fall only).

Over global ocean, and considering two main environmental conditions, the air-sea temperature difference (used as proxy of air-column stability) and background wind speed, we first have

shown that the linear relationship hypothesis which relates appropriated variables for each process represent a legitimate first guess to diagnose the atmospheric response over most of the SST gradient distribution given by mid-range resolution models. Both of mechanisms are present over a large spectrum of conditions at daily timescale. The DM is favored and has a greater impact on MABL wind divergence for mid-wind regimes in a slightly unstable to near-neutral stability conditions. PA impacts more substantially wind divergence in two distinct regimes: high background wind speed with unstable air-column and low wind speed with slightly unstable air-column. The first regime is explained by the important sensible heat fluxes and the second one by the fact that the air parcel is sufficiently present over SST structures to develop the secondary circulation [Desbiolles et al., in prep.].

Aerosols affect both directly and indirectly the Earth's radiative budget and climate. As a direct effect, aerosols interact with radiation either through scattering or absorption. The scattering of solar radiation by aerosol particles typically results in a cooling of the ground surface, while absorption of solar radiation determines local heating of the atmosphere. Moreover, as an indirect effect, in the lower atmosphere aerosols alter the microphysical and radiative properties of clouds. Thus they can influence cloud optical properties, cloud cover, cloud lifetime, and precipitation. After a sensitivity study of aerosol concentration over the Great Alp Region [Napoli et al., in rev.], we have set-up suitable simulations to study the impact of marine aerosol concentration on cloud aggregation and rainfall in a context of tropical climate. The first results show that the excess of aerosol tends to decrease significantly the total the rainfall potentially explained by the reduction of deep convective events [Desbiolles et al., in prep.].

Acknowledgement

Support for this study has been provided by HPC-TRES grant number 2020-10 and ESA contract n.4000127657/19/NL/FF/gp. We acknowledge the CINECA computing facilities and the help provided to use the resources.

References

Desbiolles, F., Alberti, M., and Meroni, A.M., Hamouda, M.E.A. and Pasquero, C. (2021) Links between sea surface temperature structures, clouds and rainfall: Study case of the Mediterranean Sea. *Geo. phys. Res. Let.*

Future projections of river floods

Di Sante, F.^{1,2}, Coppola, E.², Giorgi, F.²

¹Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS, Trieste, Italy

²Earth System Physics Section, The Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics, Trieste, Italy

Keywords: floods, climate change

One of the most largely recognized effect of the Global Warming is the change of weather extremes. The increase of extreme precipitation events is directly linked to a greater availability of precipitable water induced by a warmer atmosphere. The flood projected signals are heterogeneous and influenced by different phenomena. As an example, the rise in temperature could increase the risk of floods over the regions sensible to extreme precipitations and at the same time could reduce the risk of floods over the regions sensible to the melted snow accumulated during the cold season. In this work the CORDEX-CORE simulations completed using two different Regional Climate Models (RegCM and REMO) are used to estimate the future changes on flood risk for eight CORDEX domains (North-America, Central-America, South-America, Europe, Africa, West-Asia, East-Asia, South-East-Asia and Australasia). A river-routing model is applied to simulate the river discharge of a high resolution grid (0.06 degree) for three different driving Global Climate Models, two different scenarios (rcp2.6 and rcp8.5) and for each of the domains. The simulated discharges are hence used to fit a generalized extreme value (GEV) distribution to estimate the change on flood risk related to the future climate projections.

Fig.1 - Relative changes of multi-model ensemble mean of daily peak flow with a return period of 100 years for the RCP8.5 and the end of the 21th century.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2016-07.

References

Di Sante, F., Coppola, E., and Giorgi, F., 2021. Projections of river floods in Europe using EURO-CORDEX, CMIP5 and CMIP6 simulations. *International Journal of Climatology* 41(5), 3203-3221. <https://doi.org/10.1002/joc.7014>

Di Sante, F., García-Valdecasas Ojeda, M., Coppola, E., and Giorgi, F. Projections of river droughts and floods in the CORDEX-core domains using CORDEX, CMIP5 and CMIP6 simulations. In preparation.

The effect of correcting sub-daily climate outputs: implications for hydrological studies of extreme values

García-Valdecasas Ojeda, M.^{1,2}, Di Sante, F.^{1,2}, Nogherotto, R.^{1,2}, Raffaele, F.², Coppola, E.², and Giorgi, F.²

¹Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS, Trieste, Italy.

²International Centre for Theoretical Physics, Trieste, Italy.

Keywords: bias correction, discharge, climate change, CETEMPS hydrological model, ICTP Regional Climate Model, Italy.

Floods are one of the most devastating natural hazards, leading to strong impacts on humans and ecosystems. Under global warming, an increase in frequency and severity of flood events is expected, and therefore, a better understanding of this type of phenomenon is critical for the adaptation and mitigation of climate change.

A model chain approach based on climate and hydrological simulations to simulate river flow is a common method for studying future flood risks. Climate models are not error-free, and several authors recommend that climate datasets be corrected before being used to simulate river discharge. This method, however, is controversial, particularly when dealing with extreme values and timescales shorter than daily.

In this framework, this study investigates the impact of correcting sub-daily climate data for flood hazard assessments. For this aim, 3-hourly precipitation and temperature outputs from the ICTP Regional Climate Model (RegCM; Giorgi et al., 2012) were bias corrected using the multivariate quantile mapping bias correction algorithm by Cannon (2018). Then, raw and bias-corrected climate datasets were used to feed the CETEMPS Hydrological Model (CHyM; Coppola et al., 2007) and simulate the river discharge of the Italian river basins in both recent past and future conditions.

This work, therefore, had three different aims: (1) to examine the capability of a bias correction method to reduce errors in sub-daily climate datasets, (2) to investigate the effect of using bias-corrected climate outputs to simulate river discharge. Finally, (3) compare projections in river discharge from CHyM simulations fed with raw and bias-corrected climate datasets. The results for precipitation showed that bias correction efficiently reduced errors in terms of mean values, but it has more difficulty correcting extreme values. These results, moreover, evidenced that the ability of the method is heavily reliant on the length of the datasets used as reference. Furthermore, the improvement provided by bias correction in characterizing precipitation patterns does not always correspond to an improvement in simulating river discharge. In any case, projections of precipitation and river discharge with and without bias correction show a similar signal of change for mean and extreme values.

Fig. 1 - Relative projected changes in the annual mean discharge for two time slices (2020-2049 and 2070-2099) compared to the recent past (1976-2005) for simulations fed with raw and bias-corrected RegCM outputs driven by the HadGEM2-ES under RCP8.5 (top), and the changes in terms of extreme discharge according to Q100 (bottom).

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2020-02. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the IS CRA initiative, for the availability of high performance computing resources and support (IsraC “HYPER”).

References

- Cannon, A.J. (2018). Multivariate quantile mapping bias correction: an N-dimensional probability density function transform for climate model simulations of multiple variables. *Clim. Dyn.* 50, 31–49. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00382-017-3580-6>
- Coppola, E., Tomasetti, B., Mariotti, L., Verdecchia, M., Visconti, G. (2007). Cellular automata algorithms for drainage network extraction and rainfall data assimilation. *Hydrol. Sci. J.* 52, 579–592. <https://doi.org/10.1623/hysj.52.3.579>
- Fantini, A. (2019). Climate change impact on flood hazard over Italy. Ph.D. thesis, University of Trieste.
- Fantini, A., Coppola, E., Verdecchia, M., Giuliani, G. (In preparation). GRIPHO: a gridded high-resolution hourly precipitation dataset over Italy.
- García-Valdecasas Ojeda et al. (In preparation). Climate change impact on flood hazard over Italy.
- Giorgi, F., et al. (2012). RegCM4: model description and preliminary tests over multiple CORDEX domains. *Clim. Res.* 52, 7–29. <https://doi.org/10.3354/cr0101>

Coupling atmospheric and hydrological modelling in the context of parallel computing

Gelaw, E. B.^{1,2}, Ferraris L.¹, Parodi A.¹, Delogu F.¹, Gabellani S.¹

¹CIMA Research Foundation, Savona, Italy

²Department of Informatics, Bioengineering, Robotics and Systems Engineering (DIBRIS), University of Genoa, Genoa, Italy

Keywords: hydroinformatics, hydrological modeling, atmospheric simulation, parallel computing, model coupling

The Hydrological Model Continuum (HMC for short) (Silvestro et al., 2013) is a distributed hydrological model developed and maintained by CIMA Research Foundation in Italy. It is a highly parsimonious model with distinct compartments. Every component is implemented in a modular structure, and this PhD project is trying to parallelize the model using the Message Passing Interface (MPI) (Walker, 1994) paradigm.

The model has an energy balance component which was solved in HMC based on the well known “force-restore” approach of (Deardorff, 1978) and implemented according to the procedures of (Dickinson, 1988). The energy balance is a typical example of what is called embarrassingly

parallel part of the model.

Right now the Land Surface Model (LSM), a sub-component of the energy balance component, is completely parallelized. The parallelization was implemented based on a combination of different MPI concepts (Derived Data Types, Virtual Topology, Collective Communication) as well as the technique of Fortran allocatable arrays. Then it was tested on the Ligurian domain and the result was compared to the sequential output. As expected the parallel result was exactly the same as its sequential counterpart.

Acknowledgment

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS under HPC-TRES program award number 2019-08, and we acknowledge that.

Reference

Deardorff, J. W. (1978). Efficient prediction of ground surface temperature and moisture, with inclusion of a layer of vegetation. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, *83*(C4), 1889. <https://doi.org/10.1029/JC083iC04p01889>

Dickinson, R. E. (1988). The Force–Restore Model for Surface Temperatures and Its Generalizations. *Journal of Climate*, *1*(11), 1086–1097. [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442\(1988\)001](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0442(1988)001)

Silvestro, F., Gabellani, S., Delogu, F., Rudari, R., & Boni, G. (2013). Exploiting remote sensing land surface temperature in distributed hydrological modelling: the example of the Continuum model. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, *17*(1), 39–62. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-17-39-2013>

Walker, D. W. (1994). The design of a standard message passing interface for distributed memory concurrent computers. *Parallel Computing*, *20*(4), 657–673. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-8191\(94\)90033](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-8191(94)90033)

HPCaaS for climate data analytics at scale

Giannotta, A.¹, Elia, D.¹, D’Anca, A.¹ and Aloisio, G.^{1,2}

¹ Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui Cambiamenti Climatici, Lecce, Italy

² University of Salento, Lecce, Italy

Keywords: climate, software containers, high performance computing, big data analytics, HPCaaS

High-Performance Containers can pave the way for the High Performance Computing as a Service (HPCaaS) paradigm also in the context of climate data analytics. In particular, our solutions focus on the Ophidia High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) framework. Containerized versions of this software facilitate the deployment and portability of the software stack on almost any target system, without introducing a noticeable performance overhead.

Ophidia is a big data analytics framework able to efficiently manage large and complex workflows. It supports in-memory and parallel computations on multiple nodes in a parallel and workflow-based fashion, by using operators that are designed for multi-dimensional scientific data, such as climate datasets.

The deployment of a software managing large data volumes must be first of all scalable, but also easy to carry out for end-users and portable in order to seamlessly work on different systems. To deal with this problem, the power, portability and simplicity of containers can be exploited, which is a novel concept in HPC environments.

Lightweight software virtualization, in particular OS-level virtualization, brings containers to life, by creating an isolated software environment packaged into a so-called container image: just a single, portable and consistent file that contains applications plus all their dependencies and libraries bundled with other binaries and configuration files needed to run the software. In order to produce this result, different container engines have been evaluated and employed, always starting from the same definition and configuration files: Docker for PC users, Sylabs Singularity that is more suitable for HPC systems and Udocker as a choice to bridge HPC and Cloud-based ecosystems.

A containerized version of the Ophidia framework components has been created with the goal of targeting different infrastructures and the current solution supports distributed scenarios with the Ophidia components mapped onto different containers, communicating with each other.

A usable Python client is being developed to manage the deployment and undeployment of containerized Ophidia components with various container engines on different infrastructures.

Strong scalability tests carried out on CMCC’s Zeus supercomputer demonstrated that there is no significant performance difference between the software containerization made with Singularity and the bare-metal deployment, confirming, thus, the validity of the proposed approach.

Furthermore, besides the distributed scenario, a different deploy scenario has been considered in order to allow users to easily setup the Ophidia software on their systems, for testing and training purposes. To this end a ready-to-use single container solution has been created and is publicly accessible on DockerHub (“ophidiabigdata/ophidia-training”). With one simple command, the user can choose to instantiate: a full Ophidia software stack along with an interactive command line interface (the Ophidia Terminal) or with a web-based interface (the Jupyter Notebook).

The results of this activity show the effectiveness of the containerization approach in terms of simplified deployment and improved portability of a data analytics software, such as the Ophidia framework, across a range of different HPC/Cloud infrastructures, thus targeting the HPCaaS paradigm.

Future work will include i) improvement of the containers performance and enhancement of their features, ii) introduction of Kubernetes orchestrator for a distributed cloud-based deployment

management, iii) integration of data sharing solution to handle data on geographically distributed systems, and iv) further exploration of the use of high performance interconnect network drivers, as well as a stronger integration with the HPC software ecosystem.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2020-05. Moreover, this work was in part supported by EGI-ACE that receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101017567.

References

D. Elia, S. Fiore, A. D'Anca, C. Palazzo, I. Foster, D. N. Williams, G. Aloisio, "An in-memory based framework for scientific data analytics". In Proceedings of the ACM International Conference on Computing Frontiers (CF '16), May 16-19, 2016, Como, Italy, pp. 424-429.

S. Fiore, A. D'Anca, C. Palazzo, I. T. Foster, D. N. Williams, G. Aloisio, "Ophidia: Toward Big Data Analytics for eScience", ICCS 2013, June 5-7, 2013 Barcelona, Spain, ICCS, volume 18 of Procedia Computer Science, page 2376-2385. Elsevier, 2013.

Machine Learning for Extreme Weather Events

Immorlano, F.^{1,3}, Accarino G.^{2,3}, Chiarelli M.^{2,3}, Aloisi V.^{1,3}, Gatto A.^{1,3}, Aloisio G.^{1,3}

¹ Department of Innovation Engineering, University of Salento, Lecce, Italy

² Department of Biological and Environmental Sciences and Technologies, University of Salento, Lecce, Italy

³ Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change (CMCC) Foundation, Lecce, Italy

Keywords: machine learning, deep learning, climate change, climate science, extreme weather events, tropical cyclones

Long-term shifts in temperatures and weather patterns are known as *climate change* and, throughout the history, most of them have been caused by very small natural variations in the Earth's orbit that modified the amount of solar energy our planet receives. But since the 1800s, human activities have been the main driver of climate change, primarily due to the huge quantities of carbon dioxide released into the atmosphere starting from the industrial revolution (NASA, 2021; United Nations, 2021). One of the effects that began to manifest in recent years and that is destined to get worse over time is the intensification of Extreme Weather Events (EWEs), in particular Tropical Cyclones (TCs). They are warm-core, large-scale cyclones, originating over tropical or subtropical waters, with organized deep convection (Roy and Kovordányi, 2012) and a closed surface wind circulation about a well-defined low-pressure center. The goal of the Ph.D. research project is to increase the knowledge of climatic phenomena, with a focus on TCs, by applying Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) algorithms to tackle tasks for which traditional approaches are usually employed. Indeed, traditional models are extremely intensive from a computational standpoint and very time-consuming, while ML algorithms, after the training phase, require just few minutes or fractions of a minute to make a prediction. Moreover, they are basically data-driven approaches since they make predictions by learning complex and non-linear spatio-temporal relationships directly from data (Mudigonda et al., 2017), without needing the physical equation governing the phenomenon of interest to be specified. This means that they can learn the system behavior also in the case it is not known very well, and this happens very frequently in climate science where physical phenomena are complex and highly non-linear. First, the physics fundamentals at the basis of TCs and the main ML and DL algorithms developed for climate science use cases have been studied and carefully analyzed. An Artificial Neural Network (ANN) made up of a Long Short-Term Memory Network (LSTM) and a Convolutional LSTM has been developed for TC track forecasting i.e., the prediction of the geographical position of the TC center after 6, 12 and 24 h. The climatic fields chosen as predictors have been downloaded from the *ERA5* dataset for the North-West Pacific Basin, with a spatial resolution of $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ and a temporal resolution of 3 hours, and the information about the past TCs and their trajectories has been extracted from the *International Best Track Archive for Climate Stewardship (IBTrACS)* database. The mean errors are about 65 km and 130 km for the 12 h and the 24 h forecasts respectively and are comparable with the state-of-the-art DL approaches for TC track forecasting; moreover, the predicted trajectories are very close to the real ones and the model captured the direction of movement of the TCs. The investigation will be also extended to the use of DL for the TC Detection task i.e., the identification of the TC center in a particular time instant and on gridded climatic fields that result significant to its cyclogenesis.

Downscaling of 2-meter temperature (T2M) over the *EURO-CORDEX* domain has been the second topic of interest. It is the process of increasing the spatial resolution of climatic fields starting from their lower resolution counterpart and it is crucial resolve to climate events at a finer scale, including EWEs. To this aim, a Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) called *Multi-Scale Generative*

Adversarial Network for Statistical Downscaling has been developed to downscale the *ERA-Interim* T2M maps from about 83 km to 13 km of spatial resolution. The results show a very close match between the generated and the real maps from a perceptive standpoint, while the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) reveals some hotspots mainly located in the North-West zone, corresponding to the Atlantic Ocean which is typically characterized by low temperatures. This work has been published on *AI* journal.

Another use case that will be assessed is the *Fire Weather Index (FWI)* risk maps generation, corresponding to the computation of the fire index risk maps through significant climatic fields i.e., rain, temperature, relative humidity and wind.

Finally, thinking about the COVID-19 pandemic as an unfortunate extreme event that hit the entire world, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been exploited to forecast the second wave of hospitalizations in Italy, and the resulting work has been published on *informatics* journal. In a second use case, an ANN-based approach has been designed and developed to predict the daily effective reproduction number in Italy.

All the experiments have been conducted on the Marconi100 GPU cluster at CINECA, by means of the grant of an ISCRA Class C Project and using a single node equipped with 4 Volta V100 GPUs.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2020-04. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the ISCRA initiative, for the availability of high performance computing resources and support (IskraC “HYPER”).

References

NASA (2021), “Climate Change: How Do We Know?”, climate.nasa.gov/evidence/, Last access: 16-01-2022

United Nations (2021), “What Is Climate Change?”, www.un.org/en/climatechange/what-is-climate-change, Last access: 16-01-2022

Roy, C. and Kovordányi, R. (2012) Tropical cyclone track forecasting techniques — A review. *Atmospheric Research* 104-105, 40-69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosres.2011.09.012>

Mudigonda, M., Kim, S., Mahesh, A., Ebrahimi Kahou, S., Kashinath, K., Williams, D., Michalski, V., O’Brien, T., Prabhat, M. (2017) Segmenting and tracking extreme climate events using neural networks. *Deep Learning for Physical Sciences (DLPS) Workshop*

An HPC-enabled solution for the management of large climate analytics workflows

Musio, M.¹, Elia, D.¹, D'Anca, A.¹ and Aloisio, G.^{1,2}

¹ Advanced Scientific Computing Division, Centro Euro-Mediterraneo sui cambiamenti climatici (CMCC)

² Department of Engineering for Innovation, University of Salento

Keywords: climate workflows, HPC, big data analytics, resource management, scheduling

In recent years more and more climate-related studies are being conducted to observe and monitor changes on a global scale. This inevitably leads climate researchers to require large computing power and proper tools to conduct adequate studies on the ever-growing data. Exploiting the computing power offered by the HPC systems can be a winning choice considering that climate datasets are often already stored on HPC systems and analyzing such data on a different location would result in additional costs and resource consumption.

Workflows can help scientists to focus on their research rather than the computation management and orchestration. A workflow is simply a high-level specification of a set of tasks and the dependencies between them that must be satisfied in order to accomplish a specific goal.

Workflow management systems can support the execution of workflows, allowing scientists to automate a set of operations, such as in complex climate analysis.

Efficient management of climate analysis workflows presents a number of challenges, such as proper task scheduling that, in the context of supercomputers, is handled by HPC resource managers. These resource managers are very important technologies in HPC systems for job management, acting as a link between user requests and the cluster computing resources. These have been designed to handle large parallel processing jobs, such as climate model simulations, however they have some limitations in processing heterogeneous workflows composed of both long-running batch-oriented tasks and shorter-running tasks, such as those for data analysis. In addition, HPC resource managers perform a fixed job assignment to cluster resources and this can somehow limit the balancing of tasks in case of dynamic execution requirements.

To efficiently support the execution of large-scale climate analysis workflows on HPC systems, a new scheduling solution tailored for large-scale data analysis workflows has been developed. The system was designed with the aim to be highly scalable and able to support the allocation of dynamic and heterogeneous tasks. To this end, a widely used technology for big data applications was used: a message queue. A message queue is nothing more than a Message Oriented Middleware component capable of containing messages to facilitate communication between different entities. The RabbitMQ broker has been chosen to manage communication via queues, as it is one of the most widely used Open Source message queue brokers.

The main components of the proposed solution, as can be seen in the figure, are the **workflow manager**, the **scheduler worker**, and the **queueing system**. The first deals with the assignment to the RabbitMQ queues of the various tasks that make up a climate analysis workflow in such a way that a series of scheduler workers can consume and process them. Several scheduler workers can be instantiated and they consume tasks as soon as they are available, thus implementing a pull type consumption that favours horizontal scalability. To support the execution on HPC supercomputers the solution has been implemented so that any of these components can be instantiated on HPC compute nodes via the HPC resource manager. The new system improves the processing of large-scale climate analyses since the HPC resource manager no longer has to manage task scheduling, but only the allocation of worker components to cluster nodes.

The scheduler has been developed to optimize the management of data analytics tasks, such as the Ophidia Framework, and it represents one of the main components of the ESDM-PAV Runtime

software in the ESiWACE2 project.

To evaluate the proposed solution, a number of tests have been run on the Zeus supercomputer at CMCC exploiting the ESDM-PAV Runtime system with a workflow of Ophidia tasks. A performance comparison between the proposed solution and the HPC resource manager has been conducted. A workflow consisting of about 300 different tasks that calculates the summer days climate index on a global scale has been executed on a NetCDF dataset of daily measurements considering years from 1900 to 2000. The tests have shown how the proposed solution can positively affect the scheduling of workflows of climate data analysis, being about twice as fast as the HPC scheduler in the evaluated scenario.

Fig.1 – Overview of the proposed solution showing the scheduler components and the interactions that take place between them and the RabbitMQ queues.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2020-04. Moreover, this work was in part supported by ESiWACE2 that has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 823988.

References

- S. Jha, J. Qiu, A. Luckow, P. Mantha and G. C. Fox, "A Tale of Two Data-Intensive Paradigms: Applications, Abstractions, and Architectures," 2014 IEEE International Congress on Big Data, 2014, pp. 645-652, doi: 10.1109/BigData.Congress.2014.137
- S. Fiore et al., "Ophidia: A full software stack for scientific data analytics," 2014 International Conference on High Performance Computing & Simulation (HPCS), 2014, pp. 343-350, doi: 10.1109/HPCSim.2014.6903706.
- D. Elia, S. Fiore and G. Aloisio, "Towards HPC and Big Data Analytics Convergence: Design and Experimental Evaluation of a HPDA Framework for eScience at Scale," in IEEE Access, vol. 9, pp. 73307-73326, 2021, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3079139

“Documentation: Table of Contents.” RabbitMQ, www.rabbitmq.com/documentation.html

John, V., & Liu, X. (2017). A Survey of Distributed Message Broker Queues. ArXiv, abs/1704.00411.

Projections of the Fire Weather Index (FWI) using CORDEX-CORE simulations

Rita Nogherotto^{1,2}, Francesca Raffaele², Erika Coppola²

¹Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS, Trieste, Italy

²The Abdus Salam International Centre for Theoretical Physics, ICTP

Regional climate models (RCMs) are tools used worldwide to produce high resolution regional climate simulations. The ICTP Earth System Physics section maintains the RegCM system, which is employed by a wide scientific community. The first version of the model, RegCM1, was developed in 1989 and since then it has undergone major updates. The last version, the Regcm5, ready to be released, includes a new non hydrostatic dynamical core, more accurate and much faster than the one available in RegCM4. This version allows the model to be more easily applied at convection-permitting resolutions (1-3 km). The new model has been tested using different domains and resolutions: the big amount of testing of the new core have allowed to highlight and solve several computational issues, in particular the new cloud microphysical scheme (Nogherotto et al 2016) was tuned and debugged.

Regional climate models can be used to evaluate climate changes impacts in terms of extreme events. Within the HPC Marconi the Global ECMWF Fire Forecasting system model (Di Giuseppe 2016) was implemented and run.

Figure 1: The Fire Weather Index (FWI) system provides fire danger information following the European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS) classification: very low , low , moderate , high , very high and extreme. Upper figures show the comparison of the simulated FWI with ERA5 reanalysis. Lower figures show the mid-future changes of the FWI for two climate scenarios.

The Fire Weather Index (FWI) is a meteorologically based index used worldwide to estimate fire danger. This index has been validated and recognized as one of the most trusted and important indicators for meteorological fire danger. In the framework of the CORDEX-CORE project, we investigate how changes in relative humidity, wind, temperature and precipitation can act together in fire danger. Two regional climate models (RCM) have been used at 0.22° resolution to

downscale 3 global climate models (GCMs) from the CMIP5 project. The analysis is carried out over 9 CORDEX domains for two climate scenarios namely the RCP2.6 and the RCP8.5. All the results are put in the context of the new CMIP6 projections, which show a stronger warming signal than CMIP5 partly related to the higher ECS in several of the models compared to the previous generation GCMs. The higher resolution of the RCM ensemble allows for a more detailed description of the fire index pattern revealing details not shown by GCMs and, along with the CMIP5 and CMIP6 ones, represent an invaluable resource for climate change impact studies.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2020-12. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the ISCRA initiative, for the availability of high performance computing resources and support (IskraC "HYPER").

References:

Nogherotto, R., Tompkins, A. M., Giuliani, G., Coppola, E., & Giorgi, F. (2016). Numerical framework and performance of the new multiple-phase cloud microphysics scheme in RegCM4. 5: precipitation, cloud microphysics, and cloud radiative effects. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 9(7), 2533-2547.

Di Giuseppe, Francesca, et al. (2016). The potential predictability of fire danger provided by numerical weather prediction. *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology* 55.11. 2469-2491.

Marine Propeller Noise Propagation within a Shallow Water Environment

Petris, G.

Dipartimento di Ingegneria e Architettura, Università degli Studi di Trieste, Trieste, Italy

Keywords: underwater acoustic, propeller, Ffowcs-Williams and Hawkins, FDTD

A new methodology has been developed to evaluate the noise generated by a marine propeller, which couples the Ffowcs-Williams and Hawkins (FW-H) model with the wave equations in the physical space. The understanding of how the acoustic noise propagates in the marine environment is fundamental to mitigating the effects on the fauna. [1]

The FW-H is used to characterize the noise generated by a marine propeller. The acoustic pressure obtained through the use of FW-H, obtaining the acoustic pressure at a specific microphone [2], works as a boundary condition for the Finite-Difference-Time-Domain (FDTD) algorithm, used to solve the wave equation.

The study shows the effects of two possible configurations of the marine environment: the open-sea case and the canal case. The first case shows how the noise is propagated in an unbounded domain and taken as a reference. A dipole-like behavior of the sound pressure level is observed along the propeller blade, of which a section is shown in Figure 1 a). Figure 1 b) shows the effects of a bounded domain since, in the canal case, the acoustic waves are reflected from the air-water interface at the top of the domain and lateral and bottom walls. The sides of the canal along the x-direction are open, allowing the acoustic waves to leave the domain. The SPL, in this case, is higher than the previous case, and an increase is observed along the seabed.

The simulations have been conducted using the HPC infrastructure due to the computational required to calculate the wave equation solution with the FDTD method. In addition, the parallelization has been done with the openMP parading for a Julia code and MPI for a C code.

Fig.1 Contour of Sound Pressure Level on the x-z plane passing through the propeller axis : a) open-sea case, b) canal case.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2019-05. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the ISCRA initiative, for the availability of high-performance computing resources and support (IscraC "HMEA").

References

- [1] Hildebrand, J.A., 2009. Anthropogenic and natural sources of ambient noise in the ocean. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 395, pp.5-20.
- [2] Cianferra, M., A. Petronio, and V. Armenio. "Non-linear noise from a ship propeller in open sea condition." *Ocean Engineering* 191 (2019): 106474.

Multivariate relationship in big data collection of Ocean Observing System

Pietropolli, G.¹, Manzoni, L.¹, Cossarini, G.²

¹Università degli studi di Trieste, Trieste, Italy

²Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS, Trieste, Italy

Keywords: deep learning, float, confidence-interval, quality-check procedure

Observations are an essential component for studying the Ocean. This is particularly true considering a changing Ocean (affected by phenomena such as acidification and so on) and considering the high variability of the ocean.

Acidification reduced pH and alters both seawater chemical speciation and biogeochemical cycles of many elements and compounds. Historically, the measurements of the marine variable were performed by specific cruises that gathered water samples and subsequently analyzed them in the laboratory. This remains, also nowadays, the most accurate and reliable technique to collect marine data. However, there are significant limits. During the last twenty years, new oceanographic instruments have been introduced to perform subsurface measurements: float, glides, and so on, used and collected by the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS). Among the new technologies emerges the float, which is a two meters long robotic device collecting marine variable data diving in the ocean varying its depth through its buoyancy change. Standard float sensors measures temperature, salinity, and pressure. additionally, float can be equipped with BCG sensors (that measures chlorophyll, oxygen, nitrate, pH and so on) but the cost of building the float instruments raises drastically. Hence, are available more information about variables such as temperature, salinity and pressure, whereas other sea's parameters are measured less frequently. Among BCG sensors, oxygen is the most frequented observed variable. The use of machine learning techniques to fill these practical gaps, exploiting the big amount of marine data that has been collected during the last decades for the prediction of the relationship between the ocean's variable has been recently proposed. The advantage of such reconstruction is to predict variables that would be too expensive to achieve for a float instrument, moreover they can be used to validate theoretical models, study marine processes and so on. The scope of this work is to describe an improved neural network technique for the prediction of nutrient concentration and carbonates starting from information such as data and geolocation of the sampling, temperature, salinity and oxygen density. In this paper, a different dataset is introduced to train the model, i.e. the EMODnet dataset. Moreover, a new quality check procedure, which is intended to identify cruises with anomalous data and remove them from the dataset by directly looking at the prediction of the neural network used as model, is introduced and tested. This quality check procedure has been introduced because we are dealing with an assembling dataset, that is EMODnet, and the process of merging multiple sources can lead to errors in measurements transcriptions, or in measurements communication and so on. After this quality check of the input data, the model is retrained among the new corrected dataset. The deep learning model used, together with the two-step quality check routine introduced, lead to a wide reduction of both the fitness measures used to test the validity of the model. Finally, a confidence interval for the predictions will be provided, exploiting the concept of deep ensembles of neural network, and its validity will be validated through practical results.

Fig.1 - Boxplots of the Mean Absolute Error and of the Square Root Mean Error of measurements belonging to the validation set: (a) NO₃⁻, (b) PO₃⁻⁴, (c) Si(OH)₄, (d) AT, (e) Chlorophyll-a, (f) NH₄⁺.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number YYYY-NN. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the IS CRA initiative, for the availability of high performance computing resources and support (IsraC “HYPER”).

References

R. Sauzède, H. C. Bittig, H. Claustre, O. Pasqueron de Fommervault, J.-P. Gattuso, L. Legendre, K. S. Johnson, Estimates of water-column nutrient concentrations and carbonate system parameters in the global ocean: a novel approach based on neural networks, *Frontiers in Marine Science* 4 (2017) 128.

M. Fourier, L. Coppola, H. Claustre, F. D’Ortenzio, R. Sauzède, J.-P. Gattuso, A regional neural network approach to estimate water-column nutrient concentrations and carbonate system variables in the mediterranean sea: Canyon-med, *Frontiers in Marine Science* 7 (2020) 620.

S. C. Doney, V. J. Fabry, R. A. Feely, J. A. Kleypas, Ocean acidification: the other co₂ problem, *Annual review of marine science* 1 (2009) 169–192.

The role of HPC in scenario-based risk assessment: the case study of Isfahan, Iran

Scaini, C.¹, Damiani, A.² and Poggi, V.¹

¹Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS, Trieste, Italy

²Scuola Universitaria Superiore di Pavia – IUSS

Keywords: seismic hazard, damage assessment, earthquakes, uncertainty propagation, High Performance Computing, wrapper

On a global scale, one out of three people is exposed to earthquakes. Most casualties and injuries are caused by the damage and collapse of buildings, making seismic damage assessment a priority for emergency management in active seismic areas.

Traditionally, seismic damage assessment is performed at different scales based on ground motion estimates, exposure data (i.e. building location and characteristics) and fragility functions for the main building types. While uncertainty in the ground motion is accounted by most ground motion estimations, exposure and fragility are often represented by static layers which do not account for their associated uncertainty.

Here we present a modelling strategy aimed at estimating the uncertainty associated with damage estimates. The method is based on the existing damage assessment procedure implemented in north-eastern Italy (Poggi et al., 2020). The damage assessment is performed in near real-time based on estimated ground motion and using the OpenQuake software (<https://platform.openquake.org/>).

In order to explore the propagation of uncertainty and its impact on the resulting damage assessment, we propose to run multiple times the model taking advantage of High-Performance Computing (HPC) infrastructures. The modelling strategy is summarized in Fig. 1. A python Wrapper allows running multiple instances of OpenQuake, initialized with parameters sampled within a range of values (e.g. in form of probability density functions, Fig. 1, left). The post-processing phase allows summarizing the expected damages in form of maps associated with an uncertainty level (Fig. 1, right).

Fig.1 – Modelling strategy implemented in order to estimate the associate uncertainty of damage assessment. Input parameters (left) are associated with probability functions. The Python Wrapper allows running multiple instances of OpenQuake, initialized with different inputs. Results are post-processed into a final output associated with an uncertainty level (right).

Preliminary results are presented for the town of Isfahan, in Iran, where hazard, exposure and fragility data are available at high resolution (Kohrangi et al., 2021a,b). The methodology was defined by directly interacting with the authors of the abovementioned studies. Specific scripts and utilities have been developed in order to sample the input parameters, initialize the model and run multiple calculations using the wrapper.

A post-processing utility, currently under development, allows calculating meaningful statistics (e.g. the average damage and associated error), providing a summary of the expected damages and their distribution in the considered area.

Results also allow identifying the key parameters that influence damage and risk estimates, and prioritize the efforts in order to produce increasingly reliable estimates in future.

HPC infrastructures allow to optimize the computational effort, reduce elapsed times and produce timely results that can support decision-makers in seismic-prone areas. Future work will be devoted to exploring the case-study and extending the method to other study-areas, contributing to increase preparedness and reduce future damages/losses.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2019-03. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the ISCRA initiative, for the availability of high-performance computing resources and support (IskraC “HYPER”).

References

Poggi, V., Scaini, C., Moratto, L., Peressi, G., Comelli, P., Bragato, P.L., and Stefano Parolai; Rapid Damage Scenario Assessment for Earthquake Emergency Management. *Seismological Research Letters* 2021;; 92 (4): 2513–2530. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1785/0220200245>

Kohrangi, M., Bazzurro, P. & Vamvatsikos, D. Seismic risk and loss estimation for the building stock in Isfahan: part II—hazard analysis and risk assessment. *Bull Earthquake Eng* **19**, 1739–1763 (2021a). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-020-01037-1>

Kohrangi, M., Bazzurro, P. & Vamvatsikos, D. Seismic risk and loss estimation for the building stock in Isfahan. Part I: exposure and vulnerability. *Bull Earthquake Eng* **19**, 1709–1737 (2021b). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10518-020-01036-2>

GPS coordinate time series in NE-Italy

Tunini, L., Magrin, A. and Zuliani, D.

Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS, Trieste, Italy

Keywords: GPS, deformation, time-series, GAMIT-GLOBK, processing

The North-East Italy is a region of particular interest in tectonics because it is located on the northern front of Adria plate, which is moving against Eurasia plate with consequences on regional deformation and seismicity. Space geodesy represents a perfect tool to study it, since the Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) can provide a globally extended and high-performing dataset. OGS established a geodetic network (FReDNet) composed of 19 permanent GNSS stations dislocated throughout the Friuli Venezia Giulia region, which continuously provides real-time data and daily and hourly files in the standard RINEX format, accessible through a public ftp repository (Bragato et al., 2021). FReDNet data are processed in combination with the data coming from other geodetic networks covering the northern Italy and surrounding areas (GNSS network Antonio Marussi, EUREF European Network, Veneto GPS network, Lombardia GPS network, Piemonte GPS network, and some stations from Austrian and Slovenia networks), in order to place the regional deformation in a broader tectonic context.

The year 2021 has been deputed to reach the following objectives: 1) To process the whole dataset of GNSS stations for the period 2002-2020 with the GAMIT-GLOBK software package (Herring et al., 2018). By using CINECA servers (Galileo and Galileo100), we are able to process one-year data in ~8 hours, instead of hundreds of hours of processing using only a local machine. 2) To automatize the processing procedure to make it running it on a daily basis, in order to keep the results continuously updated. This procedure has been tested on Galileo and it is currently running on a local machine providing, on a daily basis, for each GNSS station, daily time series obtained using final and precise broadcasted orbits with a latency period of 22 days, and preliminary daily time series for the last month period, where the most recent position is relative to just 3 days before the current date. 3) To calculate preliminary velocity field for the North-East Italy (Figure 1) in both the International Reference Frame ITRF08 and the European Reference Frame EURA (Altamimi et al., 2012). 4) To further investigate the area which is undergoing major deformation (Tolmezzo and surroundings). 5) To explore different user-selected options in the processing with GAMIT-GLOBK software in order to identify the optimum workflow that would take advantage of the most recent improvements of the same software. In fact, its most recent version (GG10.71) has enhanced not only the solar radiation pressure model, i.e. the largest non-gravitational force affecting high-altitude orbits, but also the model implemented to correct the ionospheric delay, that now considers the second order term which has been shown to impact on the satellite clocks and orbits, receiver positions, reference frame origin etc.

One of the most reliable results of our work is shown in Figure 1: the preliminary velocity field for North-East Italy, derived from the GPS data covering the time period 2002-2021. Velocity has been calculated using the program tsfit of the package GAMIT-GLOBK and the Real Sigma algorithm, which takes into account of the temporal correlations within the data. It can be observed a decrease in the velocity module going from the plain area to the mountain area (Figure 1, right), suggesting a possible accumulation of the crustal deformation in the latter. In order to further investigate the local deformation, we carried out a GPS field campaign on summer 2021 (13-21 July), measuring 18 sites scattered in an area of ~30 square-km centered in Tolmezzo (Udine). The same points had been also measured in the previous field campaigns, carried out in 2006 and 2008. The data analysis will allow us to derive a detailed velocity and strain-rate field in this particular area.

Fig.1 – Preliminary results on the GPS velocity field in Friuli Venezia Giulia region in ITRF08 (left) and EURA (right) reference frames, for the period 2002-2021 (data used are up to 20/04/2021). Error ellipses indicate a 95% confidence level.

Acknowledgement

The research reported in this work has been supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2020-11. We acknowledge the CINECA award under the ISCRa initiative, for the availability of high-performing computing resources and support (IscraC IsC83_GPSIT).

References

- Altamimi, Z., M. Tivier, L., Collilieux, X. (2012). ITRF2008 plate motion model. *J. Geophys. Res.* 117, B07402, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1029/2011JB008930>
- Bragato, P. L., Comelli, P., Sara, A., Zuliani, D., Moratto, L., Poggi, V., Rossi, G., Scaini, C., Sugan, M., and Barnaba C., et al. (2021). The OGS - Northeastern Italy seismic and deformation network: Current status and outlook, *Seismol. Res. Lett.* 92, no. 3, 1704–1716, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1785/0220200372>
- Herring, T.A. and King, R., Floyd, M.A. and McClusky, S. C. (2018). GAMIT Reference Manual: GPS Analysis at MIT, Release 10.7. Department of Earth. Tech. rep., Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Cambridge, Mass. URL: http://geoweb.mit.edu/gg/Intro_GG.pdf

Gravity data restoration and modeling for the identification of buried geological structures

Zampa L. S.^{1,2}, Camerlenghi A.¹, Creati N.¹, Busetti M.¹, Lodolo E.¹, Palmieri F.¹

¹ Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e di Geofisica Sperimentale - OGS, Trieste, Italy

² Department of Mathematics and Geosciences - University of Trieste – Italy

Keywords: gravity/magnetic processing, gravity data enhancement, data restoration

During the past 60 years, the National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics (OGS) acquired a large number of gravity and magnetic data all over the Italian Peninsula and in the Mediterranean Sea. This wealth of geophysical data today would be unthinkable to acquire because of the unsustainable costs and logistic difficulties.

We have started an important recovery and homogenization activity of this immense amount of data, made through (i) a digitalization and processing of all the "vintage" gravity and magnetic data found in the Institute's archives; (ii) an evaluation of their effectiveness about their use in geophysical and geological applications, after appropriate corrections and homogenization. Specifically, three different gravity data types have been collected and merged to create highly detailed maps of gravity anomalies: (i) sea-bottom, (ii) shipborne, and (iii) land-based gravity. The correction to these gravity data involved the use of several processing steps, some of which required the development of dedicated workflows: the topographic effect and the leveling of sea surface gravity/magnetic data.

The topographic effect estimates the contribution of topography and water masses to the total gravity field, which must be removed from the records to obtain the gravity anomaly. To calculate it, we create a Python workflow that merges multiple input digital bathymetric and topographic models [1], and computes the derived gravity effect through the discretization of the final model into prism and tesseroid elements [2].

The levelling of shipborne gravity/magnetic data is a type of correction that reduces the differences between recorded values at the intersections of different surveys lines. It has been first computed using a remove-restore method that integrates the long-wavelengths of satellite altimeter gravity or global magnetic models with the short wavelengths of the shipborne data, and then with a final adjustment using a least-squares solution. This strategy allowed to reduce the range of the misfit at the line intersections by more than 50%, in the marine datasets acquired by the OGS in the Mediterranean sea between 1960 and 1980 [3, 4].

Specific attention was paid to the correction of sea bottom gravity data around the Italian coasts, which required a slightly different computation from that of the other data types, and ultimately, it involves the upward continuation of the gravity anomaly from the irregular seafloor to the mean sea surface, accomplished using the equivalent layer solution [5].

The newly restored gravity data have been analyzed in two study areas: the northern Adriatic Sea/Friulian Plain and the Manfredonia Gulf (SW Adriatic). In both studies, we were able to identify important geological discontinuities (faults) hidden below the Plio-Quaternary sediments in both off-shore and on-shore areas, where the topography and bathymetry are mainly flat and do not reveal the presence of buried structures. This task was accomplished by using gravity data enhancement algorithms, e.g., ISVD, TILT, and Terracing [6], and 2D/3D modeling using the IGMAS+ software, through which we included available seismic and borehole data as constraints to the gravity models [7].

Fig.1 - Map of (a) topography, (b) Integrated second vertical derivative (ISVD) of the Bouguer gravity anomaly, and (c) distribution of restored gravity data in the Friuli Venezia Giulia region and North Adriatic Sea. The lower panels show the 2D gravity profiles created from the gravity data using the IGMAS+ software, crossing (a) the Friulian Plain and (b) the northern Adriatic Sea.

Acknowledgement

We thank the Ente Nazionale Idrocarburi (ENI) for letting us use their shipborne and land gravity data of the northern Adriatic Sea/NE Italy and the sea-bottom data of the Gulf of Manfredonia. We also thank them for the availability of the seismic data in the Friulian Plain along which we modeled the gravimetric profiles. The research reported in this work was supported by OGS and CINECA under HPC-TRES program award number 2018-03.

References

- [1] J. Gallant, «Merging lidar with coarser DEMs for hydrodynamic modeling over large areas,» 2019.
- [2] L. Uieda, S. R. Soler, A. Pesce, V. C. Oliveira Jr, and N. Shea, «Harmonica: Forward modeling, inversion, and processing gravity and magnetic data (Version v0.1.0),» 2020.
- [3] J. Makris, C. Morelli and C. Zanolla, «The Bouguer gravity map of the Mediterranean Sea (IBCM-G),» *Boll. Geofis. Teor. Appl.*, vol. 39, p. 79–98, 1998.
- [4] C. Zanolla, C. Morelli and I. Marson, «The magnetic anomalies of the Mediterranean Sea

(IBCM-M),» *Bollettino di Geofisica Teorica ed Applicata*, vol. 39, p. 1–36, 1998.

- [5] S. R. Soler and L. Uieda, «Gradient-boosted equivalent sources,» *Geophysical Journal International*, vol. 227, p. 1768–1783, 2021.
- [6] J. D. Fairhead, *Advances in gravity and magnetic processing and interpretation*, EAGE Publications, 2016.
- [7] S. Schmdit, H.-J. Götze, C. Fichler and M. Alver, «IGMAS+ a new 3D Gravity, FTG and Magnetic Modeling Software.,» in *Geoinformatik*, 2010.
- [8] L. Uieda, V. C. F. Barbosa and C. Braitenberg, «Tesseroids: Forward-modeling gravitational fields in spherical coordinates,» *Geophysics*, vol. 81, p. F41–F48, 2016.